

IBERIFIER — Iberian Digital Media Observatory

First annual report detailing results tests of the multiformat dissemination experiments

Report

Deliverable — D2.4

Co-funded by
the European Union

Iberifier – Iberian Digital Media Observatory has received funding from the European Commission under the Call DIGITAL-2023-DEPLOY-04, European Digital Media observatory (EDMO) — National and multinational hubs, with the reference IBERIFIER Plus - 101158511

Programme: Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL)
Call: Accelerating the best use of technologies (DIGITAL-2023-DEPLOY-04)
Work program topic: European Digital Media observatory (EDMO) – National and multinational hubs
Grant Agreement: IBERIFIER Plus - 101158511
Project coordinator: Ramón Salaverría (University of Navarra)
Term: May 1, 2024 – Oct 31, 2026 (30 months)
Report submission date: July 15, 2025
Dissemination level: Public
Task 2.6: Experimentation with innovative formats for content distribution to fight against misinformation
Deliverable Task Leader(s): Alba Tobella, Pablo Hernández-Escayola

Cite this Report as:

Tobella, A., Hernández-Escayola, P., De Lara, A., García, A., Valero, J.M., Arias, F., Carrillo, N. (2025) *Primer informe anual que detalla los resultados de las pruebas de difusión multiformato*. IBERIFIER. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15914063>

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1. Report Presentation

The experimental design aims to evaluate the effectiveness of various parameters related to short-form audiovisual content, with the objective of identifying the audiovisual features that optimize both comprehension and acceptance of truthfulness by viewers when it comes to verification content. The study focuses on video content designed for the TikTok platform.

This research targets a young population, considering two distinct environments: a university setting and a secondary school context, as this demographic is particularly active in the consumption of digital information. By choosing video as the primary medium, the study aligns with the preferences of this audience, who tend to engage more with audiovisual content due to its accessibility and appeal.

Experimental workshops will be conducted in controlled environments, where participants will be exposed to different versions of the same verification message, each with technical variations based on the parameters to be tested by the fact-checking organizations Maldita and Verificat. Prior to the final experimental phase (scheduled for 2026), a pre-test phase will take place in 2025 to make any necessary methodological adjustments.

Data will be collected through questionnaires designed to measure participants' perceptions of trustworthiness, clarity, and satisfaction with each format. The findings will help determine which elements have the greatest impact on a video's ability to effectively verify false information. Investigating the most engaging formats for conveying verified content is crucial in an environment where disinformation spreads widely through social networks and digital platforms. This is particularly significant for younger audiences, whose media consumption is largely driven by video-based social platforms. Disinformation content tends to be better adapted to these environments than rigorously verified information. Therefore, it is essential to deepen our understanding of how to improve the dissemination strategies of verification content in short video formats.

Furthermore, the rapid spread of false news requires that verification strategies not only be accurate but also engaging and easily accessible in order to capture the viewer's attention. Identifying the audiovisual elements that enhance understanding and trust may enable communicators and fact-checkers to tailor their tools to different audiences and digital environments, thereby generating a more meaningful impact in reducing the credibility of disinformation.

2. Systematic Analysis of the Reviewed Literature

A bibliographic analysis has been conducted on studies that implemented experiments with characteristics similar to those intended in our research design.

Searches were carried out in the academic database Scopus using the following terms:

1) students AND experiment AND information AND "fake news".

This initial search yielded 20 articles.

2) students AND experiment AND fake news OR disinformation.

Resulted in a total of 59 articles.

Ultimately, the systematic review was conducted on 15 articles that met the established criteria. Studies were excluded if, despite mentioning an experimental design, they consisted solely of surveys without any further interaction, were unrelated to social sciences or related disciplines, or did not include student populations—one of the core parameters of the search.

The subsequent analysis classified the selected studies according to the following variables relevant to our experimental design: number of participants; in-person or online format; method of data collection; participant profile; country; presence or absence of training; and the experiment's objectives.

The thematic areas of the journals publishing these articles include:

- Information Science and Library Studies
- Social Sciences and Humanities
- Psychology and Human Behavior
- Communication and Media Studies
- Human-Computer Interaction and Information Technologies

The analysis of the 15 selected articles from the systematic review is presented below.

Most of the reviewed studies address the impact of disinformation by focusing either on the perception of fake news or on strategies to counter it. For example, Amaro et al. (2024) analyze how the creation of false information affects users' perceptions of digital tools, while Bastick (2021) explores whether disinformation can unconsciously alter individual behavior. In the health context, Salas-Páramo and Escandón-Barbosa (2022) examine how disinformation influences the perceptions of individuals intending to get vaccinated against COVID-19. Other studies, such as those by Wolverton & Stevens (2020) and Dumitru (2020), assess the ability to identify fake news, with Dumitru focusing specifically on children and adolescents.

Other articles take a thematic approach. For instance, Wright et al. (2021) investigate how media portrayals related to disinformation impact public perceptions of immigration, taking into account sociodemographic factors. In a related study, Wright et al. (2023) examine how printed and audiovisual media representations of the Black Lives Matter (BLM) movement influence attitudes toward African Americans.

Several of the analyzed studies explore strategies to combat disinformation through educational interventions and practices aimed at improving users' critical thinking skills. Apuke et al. (2023) examine how multimedia visual instructions can increase awareness of false content, while Fendt et al. (2023) propose specific strategies to enhance the ability to distinguish between true and false information. In a similar line, Šuminas and Jastramskis (2020) assess the impact of media literacy education on the ability to judge the credibility of news, highlighting the importance of media literacy. Additionally, Tandoc et al. (2023) analyze how familiarity with the source and context—whether interpersonal or group-based—affects the credibility of information corrections.

Number of participants	In person / online
62	In person
470	mix
233	In person
60	online
54	In person
312	In person
44	In person
760	online
217	In person
30	In person
40	In person
114	mix
117	online
196	online
385	online

Table 1. Number of participants and modality of the experiment

Sample Size and Format

The largest samples, such as studies with 760, 470, and 385 participants, tend to use online or hybrid modalities. This is likely due to the fact that online methodologies facilitate the participation of large samples by eliminating logistical barriers related to transportation or geographical location. Studies with smaller samples—such as those involving 30, 40, 44, and 54 participants—are mostly conducted in person. Direct

interaction is often more suitable for smaller groups, as it allows for tighter control of the experimental environment.

Content Tested in the Reviewed Studies

The analyzed studies focus on testing various types of content, ranging from cancer-related rumors, fabricated information, and COVID-19 disinformation, to sociopolitical topics such as perceptions of immigration and refugees.

Most experiments use fabricated content created specifically for the research, including news articles, websites, memes, or social media posts. This allows researchers to control experimental variables and measure the impact of exposure to false or manipulated information. For instance, the creation of fake news and manipulation of content (positive, negative, or neutral) are common approaches to examine how such content affects participants' perceptions, emotions, or behavior.

Several studies explore the influence of familiar versus unfamiliar sources and the context in which content is presented (e.g., group chats, interpersonal exchanges). This highlights a focus on source credibility and the role of trust in the acceptance of false information. Some experiments examine socially relevant topics, such as perceptions of immigration and refugees, using different media portrayals (positive and negative) to observe their impact on public opinion. Others, such as studies on personality traits and susceptibility to fake news, aim to establish links between psychological vulnerability and gullibility in the face of manipulated information.

Experimental Design Described in the Reviewed Studies

Most experiments include both control and experimental groups, allowing researchers to compare the impact of false or manipulated content against neutral or factual information. For example, in an experiment on COVID-19 fake news, a controversial statement is introduced to the experimental group to measure its acceptance compared to a control group.

Several studies employ measurement tools such as Likert scales to gauge levels of agreement or disagreement, contextual variables (e.g., high/low attention), and control over interaction formats (personalized, group, or individual).

Both quantitative and qualitative methods are used, ranging from questionnaires to direct observation, open discussions, and behavioral analysis.

Inclusion of Training Components

Some of the studies analyzed incorporate educational components into their experimental design, which is particularly relevant given the potential for transferability.

A notable example is Dumitru (2020), who included educational activities as part of the experiment. These involved providing participants with explanations about the topic and emphasizing the importance of recognizing false content in digital environments. This approach was complemented by open discussions following the experiment, aimed at deepening the understanding of strategies used by children and adolescents to identify disinformation.

Such initiatives not only assess the effectiveness of various methods but also have the potential to enhance critical skills with practical applications in educational and media literacy contexts.

Reviewed Bibliographic Sample

Amaro, I., Barra, P., Della Greca, A., Francese, R., & Tucci, C. (2024). Believe in artificial intelligence? A user study on the ChatGPT's fake information impact. *IEEE Transactions on Computational Social Systems*.

Apuke, O. D., Omar, B., Tunca, E. A., & Gever, C. V. (2023). The effect of visual multimedia instructions against fake news spread: A quasi-experimental study with Nigerian students. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*.

Bastick, Z. (2021). Would you notice if fake news changed your behavior? An experiment on the unconscious effects of disinformation. *Computers in Human Behavior*.

Chua, A. Y. K., & Banerjee, S. (2018). Intentions to trust and share online health rumors: An experiment with medical professionals. *Computers in Human Behavior*.

Dumitru, E.-A. (2020). Testing children and adolescents' ability to identify fake news: A combined design of quasi-experiment and group discussions. *Societies*.

Fendt, M., Nistor, N., Scheibenzuber, C., & Artmann, B. (2023). Sourcing against misinformation: Effects of a scalable lateral reading training based on cognitive apprenticeship. *Computers in Human Behavior*.

Fernández-López, M., & Perea, M. (2020). Language does not modulate fake news credibility, but emotion does. *Psicologica*.

Klimova, A. M., Chmel, K. Sh., & Savin, N. Yu. (2020). Believe it or not: Public opinion and rumors about Covid-19. *Monitoring Obshchestvennogo Mneniya: Ekonomicheskie i Sotsial'nye Peremeny*.

Luo, C., Liu, J., Yang, T., & Xu, J. (2023). Combating disinformation or reinforcing cognitive bias: Effect of Weibo poster's location disclosure. *Media and Communication*.

Salas-Paramo, J., & Escandon-Barbosa, D. (2022). The moderating effect of fake news on the relationship between behavioral patterns and vaccines. *Cogent Social Sciences*.

Šuminas, A., & Jastramskis, D. (2020). The importance of media literacy education: How Lithuanian students evaluate online news content credibility. *Central European Journal of Communication*.

Tandoc, E. C., Jr., Lee, J. C. B., Lee, C. S., Sin, J. S. C., & Seet, S. K. (2023). No “Me” in misinformation: The role of social groups in the spread of, and fight against, fake news. *Mobile Communication in Asia*.

Wolverton, C., & Stevens, D. (2020). The impact of personality in recognizing disinformation. *Online Information Review*.

Wright, C., Brinklow-Vaughn, R., Johannes, K., & Rodriguez, F. (2021). Media portrayals of immigration and refugees in hard and fake news and their impact on consumer attitudes. *Howard Journal of Communications*.

Wright, C., Gatlin, K., Acosta, D., & Taylor, C. (2023). Portrayals of the Black Lives Matter movement in hard and fake news and consumer attitudes toward African Americans. *Howard Journal of Communications*.

3. Experimental Design

Objective of the Experiment

The objective is to test a series of variables related to the format of fact-checking videos among a young audience, in order to identify the most comprehensible and engaging format.

- *Comprehensibility* refers to how well the message is understood.
- *Appeal* refers to aspects of the format, such as duration and presentation.

Number of Participants

The target is to include 200 participants, with balanced representation between secondary school students and university students. This sample size is within the appropriate range for this type of experiment, according to the literature reviewed.

In-Person Modality

It is proposed that the experiment be conducted in person, as this allows for richer methodological possibilities: follow-up discussions that can provide additional insights, greater control over the various stages, and a more enriching educational experience. Furthermore, it ensures better control of the experimental environment.

The experimental workshops will be held at participating secondary schools and at Miguel Hernández University of Elche. In all cases, the necessary consent will be obtained for conducting the workshops, along with approval from the Office of Responsible Research.

Topic of the Video Content

The selected topic for the test videos is disinformation related to climate change. This subject was chosen because it is one in which fact-checkers consistently detect high levels of disinformation. Moreover, climate change is a matter of particular concern for young people, the target demographic for this study.

Data Collection Method

An online questionnaire (via Google Forms) will be administered after the viewing of the videos, and/or a paper-based questionnaire will be used in secondary schools, as it is more practical for data collection in this context. An open discussion will also be

conducted and recorded in a research journal. One of the researchers will take observational notes during these sessions.

Participant Profile

The sample will consist of university and secondary school students (aged 14 and above), with the aim of ensuring representativeness of the student population. Therefore, efforts will be made to include individuals from various academic disciplines and of different genders, as these will be the two primary variables considered in the analysis.

Variables to be Analyzed

- The format to be tested is short-form video for TikTok.
- Based on a specific bibliographic review of audiovisual content, and drawing on the experience of the fact-checkers involved in the experimental design, the specific variables to be tested will be determined.
- Some of the potential variables under study include:
 - Gender of the person presenting the video: woman vs. man with similar characteristics
 - Video adapted for a teenage audience versus video adapted for a university audience
 - Language: videos in Spanish and Catalan
 - Video duration: videos under one minute versus videos exceeding one minute
 - Format: horizontal versus vertical
 - Other variables to be considered

Initially, and for the pre-test phase, it is decided to present the videos to be tested in pairs of similar videos differing only in the variable under examination. Based on the preliminary results, the suitability of this approach will be reconsidered.

Questionnaires

Brief questionnaires are designed and tailored to each participant profile: one specifically for university students and another for school students. The explanation and use of certain terms will vary to improve comprehension for each group.

For the pre-test phase, the following questionnaire has been designed and tested (Annex I):

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSf69eJJrm92J50xGkmjuhF0ILrK9t-gQ8mAApVJKVTZAuoJFg/viewform?usp=dialog>

The questionnaire begins with general questions to contextualize the participant's profile (age, educational level, frequency of social media use, etc.), followed by a series of specific questions after viewing a video. These include Likert-type scales to assess aspects such as:

- Clarity of content
- Level of interest generated
- Trust in the source

Open-ended fields are also included to capture spontaneous impressions, suggestions, or emotional perceptions related to the video, allowing for nuances that are difficult to identify through closed-ended questions alone.

The questionnaire designed for the school-age population will be similar but adapted in terminology and tone to suit the age group. There is also consideration of collecting information through other methods more appropriate for this audience, such as a researcher's diary.

Experimental Design by Phases and Groups

The possibility of working with two initial groups—school students and university students—is proposed. These will be further divided into three experimental groups:

- Receives training prior to video viewing and open discussion.
- Receives training after video viewing and before the open discussion.
- Control group that receives training at the end, after video viewing and discussion.

The final open discussion aims to leverage participant feedback to enrich the video formats being developed, while respecting both methodological rigor and the creativity and logic of the social media platforms where these contents are published.

Session Duration

It is preferred that the session does not exceed one hour, including video viewing per group, explanation, and open discussion.

Pretest and Preliminary Results

Date Conducted: April 30, 2025

The sample consisted of 25 university students aged between 18 and 24 years, except for one participant aged between 35 and 44 years. Most were enrolled in Social Sciences degrees, and regarding gender, 68% were men and 32% women.

Four videos were tested, specifically those explaining a concept related to climate change. The pretest was conducted under the same conditions planned for the main experiment, with the university setting selected for this phase.

The focus variables in this pretest were the presenter's gender for videos produced by Maldita and the language variable for the pair of videos provided by Verificat.

In both cases, the sample consisted of 25 students.

4. First results / Pretest

General Consumption of Videos and Fact-Checking Videos: MALDITA Videos

The general consumption of videos within the sample is very high but decreases when participants are specifically asked about videos whose content aims to verify or debunk information.

The first chart shows that 76% of respondents consume video content on the internet or social media very frequently (several times a week), while 24% consume it frequently (once a week). In other words, all participants consume this type of content at least on a weekly basis, reflecting that video is a dominant channel of media exposure in this population.

However, the second chart reveals a striking contrast: only 20% consume videos that debunk or verify information very frequently, and 8% report never consuming them. The majority, 40%, consume such content occasionally, and 32% do so only 1–2 times per month.

This suggests that although young people are extensively exposed to video format content, videos aimed at fact-checking are not a regular part of their media diet.

Figure 1: Frequency of consumption / Own elaboration

Figure 2: Frequency of consumption of fact-checking videos / Own elaboration

On the Clarity of the Videos: Video 1 Presented by a Young Woman and Video 2 Presented by a Young Man – MALDITA Videos

Video 1, presented by the young woman, achieved better results in terms of overall clarity and “very clear” ratings, as shown in Figure 3. Specifically, 60% of respondents considered the video “clear,” and an additional 16% rated it as “very clear.” Only 4% perceived it as “unclear,” and 20% rated it as “average.”

In comparison, for Video 2, presented by the young man, 56% rated it as “clear” and only 8% as “very clear” (Figure 4). While Video 2 maintains a good level of clarity (64% positive), there is a noticeable decrease compared to Video 1.

Overall, it is noteworthy that in both cases there is not a high percentage of participants classifying these videos as “very clear.”

Figure 3: Clarity of videos, female presenter / Own elaboration

Figure 4: Clarity of videos, male presenter / Own elaboration

On the Trust Conveyed by the Speaker On Camera: Video 1 Presented by a Young Woman and Video 2 Presented by a Young Man – MALDITA Videos

The video presented by the woman receives a higher overall trust rating (68%) according to Figure 5, compared to the man’s video (60%) shown in Figure 6, although the latter records a slight increase in the “very trustworthy” rating (12% versus 8%).

The higher percentage of “neutral” responses in Figure 6 may reflect a more lukewarm or less decisive reception of the message, which could be due to variables such as communication style or body language.

It is important to note that although the gender difference in presentation may have an effect, other factors such as intonation and pacing should also be considered—variables that are very difficult to isolate in this type of experiment.

Figure 5: Credibility of videos, female presenter / Own elaboration

Figure 6: Credibility of videos, male presenter / Own elaboration

On the Usefulness of the Videos for Identifying False Information – MALDITA Videos

Both videos are generally considered useful (over 80% in both cases). However, the video with the male presenter (Figure 8) shows a slight improvement in the more positive ratings (“yes, quite a bit”), whereas the video with the female presenter shows a higher concentration in the intermediate range (“a little”).

Again, both videos receive only 8% of responses in the highest category, suggesting that neither video achieves a strong impact on the perception of skill improvement.

Twice as many participants indicated that the video with the male presenter did not help them (8% vs. 4%), which could be a relevant indication if factors such as tone, communication style, or perception biases are further examined.

The fact that fewer than 10% perceive the videos as “very useful” points to an opportunity for improvement in instructional design, format, or narrative of the materials.

Figure 7: Improvement in ability to identify false information from videos, female presenter / Own elaboration

Figure 8: Improvement in ability to identify false information from videos, male presenter / Own elaboration

Regarding the language variable. VERIFICAT videos

The majority of respondents classify the content of the video shown in Figure 9 as either average (“Normal”) or high (“Clear”), with 68% of responses indicating acceptable or positive comprehension. However, a significant percentage (28%) consider it unclear or very unclear, suggesting that certain communicative elements could be improved. On the other hand, the video in Catalan shows a notable decrease in perceived clarity. Sixty-eight percent of respondents rated the content as unclear or very unclear, representing an almost exact reversal compared to video 3. Only 8% considered it clear, and no participant rated it as “very clear.” This disparity is significant and calls for reflection on the context.

Graph 9: Comprehension Ability. Spanish / Own elaboration

Graph 10: Comprehension Ability. Catalan / Own elaboration

Reflections after the pretest

- The questionnaire designed for the university population proved to be

adequate in terms of comprehension and handling by the participants. However, in order to capture a wider and more varied range of perceptions about the videos, a hybrid design is proposed for the experimental phase:

- First, videos will be shown in pairs, ensuring that the paired videos are as similar as possible except for the variable being tested. These videos will be produced by Maldita.
 - In a second phase, verification videos with no similarities will be shown to ask more open-ended questions about different aspects. These videos will be produced by Verificat.
- A relevant issue highlighted during the pretest is the impact of language on the comprehension and reception of the content. It was observed that the Catalan version generated a significantly lower perception of clarity compared to the Spanish version, probably because a large part of the students do not have Catalan or Valencian as their native language. This factor should be carefully considered and managed in the experimental phase to avoid biases derived from language.
 - About the order of presentation of the videos:
 - Importance of order: It is recognized that the impact of videos can vary depending on the order in which they are viewed.
 - Possibilities discussed:
 - Maintain a fixed order for all participants.
 - Do not change the order between groups
 - Regarding the sample characteristics, gender balance should be achieved and the sample should be increased to obtain more robust results.
 - It is also proposed to reduce the number of isolated variables tested for the compared videos and increase the number of open-ended questions and responses for the non-compared videos, so that this will also allow for the collection of other, more qualitative information.

5. General Timeline of the Experiment

FIRST PHASE 2024-2025		
Coordination		
Bibliographic review and definition of objectives	June 2024 - September 2024	UMH
Experiment design	October 2024-January 2025	ALL
Definition of variables to be tested	January 2025	Maldita and Verificat
Production of videos by the verifiers	February-March-April 2025	Maldita and Verificat
Carrying out the methodological test phase	April 30, 2025	UMH
Analysis of first results	May-june 2025	ALL
Writing the first report	July 2025	ALL
SEGUNDA FASE 2025-2026		
Design of the student recruitment protocol	September- October 2025	ALL
Establishment of the definitive hypotheses associated with the variables and aspects to be tested	October- November	ALL
Design of training materials	November- December 2026	ALL
Production of videos by the verifiers	January-February 2026	Maldita and Verificat
Carrying out the experiment	October - April 2026	UMH and Learn to Check
Analysis of Results	May 2026	ALL
Conclusions and drafting of the second report (Deadline: October 31, 2026)	June-September 2026	ALL

6. Annexes

6.1. Annex 1. Questionnaire

Disponible aquí: <https://forms.gle/6DkK9ejKc2CbqDwAA>

Y aquí:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1lIbszo01liCB8dMdUi3wURuNa_9jMB6/view?usp=sharing

Taller de verificación de contenidos: probando formatos

Proyecto IBERIFIER PLUS de lucha contra la desinformación.

* Indicates required question

El presente formulario está orientado a la investigación sobre formatos adecuados para la verificación de contenidos: <https://iberifier.eu/>

DATOS BÁSICOS

Contesta los siguientes datos básicos:

1. ¿Cuál es tu edad? *

Check all that apply.

- 18-24 años
- 25-34 años
- 35-44 años
- más de 45 años

2. ¿Qué nivel educativo te encuentra cursando? *

Mark only one oval.

- Grado
- Posgrado
- Doctorado

3. ¿Con qué género te identificas? *

Mark only one oval.

- Hombre
- Mujer
- Prefiero no decirlo

4. Rama de conocimiento de tus estudios: *

INFORMACIÓN SOBRE CONSUMO DE CONTENIDOS DE VERIFICACIÓN

Contesta a estas preguntas sobre hábitos de consumo de contenidos:

5. **¿Con qué frecuencia consumes contenido en vídeo en internet o redes sociales?** *

Mark only one oval.

- Nunca
- Ocasionalmente (1-2 veces al mes)
- Frecuentemente (semanalmente)
- Muy frecuentemente (varias veces por semana)

6. **¿Con qué frecuencia consumes contenido en vídeo que desmiente o contrasta si una información es verdadera o falsa?** *

Mark only one oval.

- Nunca
- Ocasionalmente (1-2 veces al mes)
- Frecuentemente (semanalmente)
- Muy frecuentemente (varias veces por semana)

VÍDEOS NÚMERO 1 y 2: visualiza una vez estos dos vídeos y contesta a las siguientes preguntas

1) [https://urjdefense.com/v3/_https://vm.tiktok.com/ZMkaooBXb/_!!D9dNQwwGXtA!WKXw0QjKMDdjW5F4xqvrwIU3CDcwuH4sOfWGVOpnUaxoPt2qsuuwAJtA9LMfGsrV2q1p1V3irsw9zsvh_I\\$](https://urjdefense.com/v3/_https://vm.tiktok.com/ZMkaooBXb/_!!D9dNQwwGXtA!WKXw0QjKMDdjW5F4xqvrwIU3CDcwuH4sOfWGVOpnUaxoPt2qsuuwAJtA9LMfGsrV2q1p1V3irsw9zsvh_I$)

2)

https://drive.google.com/file/d/10ddWYKMQtF3tku0_g2XwDhJ-ajWXUd9D/view?usp=sharing

7. **¿Qué diferencias encuentras entre el vídeo NÚMERO 1 y el NÚMERO 2?** *

8. ¿Qué tan claro y comprensible fue el contenido del vídeo **NÚMERO 1**? *

Mark only one oval.

- Nada claro
- Poco claro
- Normal
- Claro
- Muy claro

9. ¿Qué tan claro y comprensible fue el contenido del vídeo **NÚMERO 2**? *

Mark only one oval.

- Nada claro
- Poco claro
- Normal
- Claro
- Muy claro

10. ¿El vídeo **NÚMERO 1** mantuvo tu atención durante toda la duración? *

Mark only one oval.

- No, lo dejé antes de terminar
- Sí, pero en algunos momentos perdí interés
- Sí, lo vi completo sin distracciones

11. ¿El vídeo **NÚMERO 2** mantuvo tu atención durante toda la duración? *

Mark only one oval.

- No, lo dejé antes de terminar
- Sí, pero en algunos momentos perdí interés
- Sí, lo vi completo sin distracciones

12. ¿El formato y apariencia del video **NÚMERO 1** te pareció adecuado? *

Mark only one oval.

- No fue adecuado
 Neutral
 Sí, fue adecuado

13. ¿El formato y apariencia del video **NÚMERO 2** te pareció adecuado? *

Mark only one oval.

- No fue adecuado
 Neutral
 Sí, fue adecuado

14. ¿Cómo calificarías la credibilidad (confianza) de la información presentada en el vídeo **NÚMERO 1**? *

Mark only one oval.

- No confiable
 Poco confiable
 Neutral
 Confiable
 Muy confiable

15. ¿Cómo calificarías la credibilidad (confianza) de la información presentada en el vídeo **NÚMERO 2**? *

Mark only one oval.

- No confiable
- Poco confiable
- Neutral
- Confiable
- Muy confiable

16. ¿Te ayudó el video **NÚMERO 1** a mejorar tu capacidad para identificar información falsa? *

Mark only one oval.

- No, no me ayudó
- Un poco
- Sí, bastante
- Mucho, me pareció contenido muy útil

17. ¿Te ayudó el video **NÚMERO 2** a mejorar tu capacidad para identificar información falsa? *

Mark only one oval.

- No, no me ayudó
- Un poco
- Sí, bastante
- Mucho, me pareció contenido muy útil

18. ¿Cuál de los dos compartirías entre tus contactos? *

Mark only one oval.

- VÍDEO NÚMERO 1
- VÍDEO NÚMERO 2
- LOS DOS
- NINGUNO

19. Da alguna razón que justifique tu respuesta anterior: *

VIDEOS NÚMERO 3 y 4: : visualiza una vez estos dos vídeos y contesta a las siguientes preguntas

Vídeo número 3: <https://www.instagram.com/p/DFazofYNDMB/>

Vídeo número 4: https://www.instagram.com/reel/CjpWLPZoMB_/

20. ¿Qué diferencias encuentras entre el vídeo NÚMERO 3 y el NÚMERO 4? *

21. ¿Qué tan claro y comprensible fue el contenido del vídeo **NÚMERO 3**? *

Mark only one oval.

- Nada claro
- Poco claro
- Normal
- Claro
- Muy claro

22. ¿Qué tan claro y comprensible fue el contenido del vídeo **NÚMERO 4**? *

Mark only one oval.

- Nada claro
- Poco claro
- Normal
- Claro
- Muy claro

23. ¿El vídeo **NÚMERO 3** mantuvo tu atención durante toda la duración? *

Mark only one oval.

- No, lo dejé antes de terminar
- Sí, pero en algunos momentos perdí interés
- Sí, lo vi completo sin distracciones

24. ¿El vídeo **NÚMERO 4** mantuvo tu atención durante toda la duración? *

Mark only one oval.

- No, lo dejé antes de terminar
- Sí, pero en algunos momentos perdí interés
- Sí, lo vi completo sin distracciones

25. ¿El formato y apariencia del video **NÚMERO 3** te pareció adecuado? *

Mark only one oval.

- No fue adecuado
 Neutral
 Sí, fue adecuado

26. ¿El formato y apariencia del video **NÚMERO 4** te pareció adecuado? *

Mark only one oval.

- No fue adecuado
 Neutral
 Sí, fue adecuado

27. ¿Cómo calificarías la credibilidad (confianza) de la información presentada en el vídeo **NÚMERO 3**? *

Mark only one oval.

- No confiable
 Poco confiable
 Neutral
 Confiable
 Muy confiable

28. ¿Cómo calificarías la credibilidad (confianza) de la información presentada en el vídeo **NÚMERO 4**? *

Mark only one oval.

- No confiable
 Poco confiable
 Neutral
 Confiable
 Muy confiable

29. ¿Te ayudó el video **NÚMERO 3** a mejorar tu capacidad para identificar información falsa? *

Mark only one oval.

- No, no me ayudó
 Un poco
 Sí, bastante
 Mucho, me pareció contenido muy útil

30. ¿Te ayudó el video **NÚMERO 4** a mejorar tu capacidad para identificar información falsa? *

Mark only one oval.

- No, no me ayudó
 Un poco
 Sí, bastante
 Mucho, me pareció contenido muy útil

31. ¿Cuál de los dos compartirías entre tus contactos? *

Mark only one oval.

VÍDEO NÚMERO 3

VÍDEO NÚMERO 4

LOS DOS

NINGUNO

32. Da alguna razón que justifique tu respuesta anterior: *

Código de Investigación Responsable

Este proyecto ha sido aprobado por el Comité de Ética e Integridad en la Investigación de la Universidad Miguel Hernández. El proyecto se llevará a cabo de acuerdo a la normativa vigente y a los principios éticos internacionales aplicables

Con el fin de que pueda decidir si desea participar en este proyecto, es importante que entienda por qué es necesaria esta investigación, lo que va a implicar su participación, cómo se va a utilizar su información y sus posibles beneficios, riesgos y molestias. En este documento podrá encontrar información detallada sobre el proyecto. Por favor, tómese el tiempo necesario para leer atentamente la información proporcionada a continuación y nosotros le aclararemos las dudas que le puedan surgir. Cuando haya comprendido el proyecto se le solicitará que firme el consentimiento informado si desea participar en él.

Si decide participar en este estudio debe saber que lo hace voluntariamente y que podrá, así mismo, abandonarlo en cualquier momento. En el caso en que decida suspender su participación, ello no va a suponer ningún tipo de penalización ni pérdida o perjuicio en sus derechos y/o relación con los investigadores.

El proyecto se llevará a cabo en Elche, durante el año 2025 y 2026.

¿POR QUÉ SE REALIZA ESTE PROYECTO?

Existen estudios que demuestran que la población tiene problemas para identificar el contenido falso. Pero no se conocen estudios que demuestren los problemas concretos que subyacen a dicha identificación. En este estudio pretendemos analizar tendencias y aspectos propios de la comunicación que dificultan y/o facilitan la lucha contra la desinformación.

¿CUÁL ES EL OBJETIVO DEL PROYECTO?

Analizar tendencias y aspectos propios de la comunicación que dificultan y/o facilitan la lucha contra la desinformación

¿CÓMO SE VA A REALIZAR EL ESTUDIO?

La duración del estudio se prolongará durante un periodo de tiempo de 24 meses, pero este periodo podrá ser mayor o menor (en función del estudio).

¿QUÉ BENEFICIOS PUEDO OBTENER POR PARTICIPAR EN ESTE ESTUDIO?

Usted recibirá el mismo trato participe o no en el proyecto. En consecuencia, no obtendrá ningún beneficio directo con su participación. No obstante, la información que nos facilite, así como la que se obtenga de los análisis que se realicen, pueden ser de gran utilidad para mejorar el conocimiento que tenemos hoy día sobre la desinformación y ello permitirá idear formas de prevención, manejo y tratamiento mejores que las que poseemos en la actualidad. Por su participación en el estudio no obtendrá compensación económica.

¿QUÉ RIESGOS PUEDO SUFRIR POR PARTICIPAR EN EL ESTUDIO?

No hay ningún riesgo físico ni mental. Solo recogemos opinión.

¿QUÉ DATOS SE VAN A RECOGER?

Área de conocimiento de los estudios cursados, género y edad

¿CÓMO SE TRATARÁN MIS DATOS PERSONALES Y CÓMO SE PRESERVARÁ LA CONFIDENCIALIDAD?

La UMH, como Responsable del tratamiento de sus datos personales, le informa que estos datos serán tratados de conformidad con lo dispuesto en el Reglamento (UE) 2016/679 de 27 de abril (RGPD) y la Ley Orgánica 3/2018 de 5 de diciembre (LOPDGDD)

El acceso a su información personal quedará restringido a Alicia de Lara González además de los investigadores Félix Arias, Miguel Carvajal, Alba García Ortega, José Alberto García Avilés y José María Valero, todos ellos pdi de la UMH, cuando se precise, para comprobar los datos y procedimientos del estudio, pero siempre manteniendo la confidencialidad de los mismos de acuerdo a la legislación vigente. El Investigador/a, cuando procese y trate sus datos tomará las medidas oportunas para protegerlos y evitar el acceso a los mismos de terceros no autorizados.

* Responsable del tratamiento: Universidad Miguel Hernández de Elche, Secretaría General; CIF: Q-5350015-C.

Contacto de la delegada de protección de datos de la UMH: dpd@umh.es

* Responsable interno del tratamiento: Alicia de Lara González

* Contacto: Además de poder contactar con el investigador/a principal, puede contactar con la delegada de protección de datos de la UMH: dpd@umh.es

* Finalidad: Realizar el tratamiento de sus datos personales para poder participar en este proyecto de investigación

* Legitimación: Artículos 6.1.a) y 9.2.a del RGPD: El interesado da su consentimiento explícito para el tratamiento de sus datos personales para la realización del presente proyecto de investigación.

* Obligación o no de facilitar datos y consecuencias de no hacerlo: No aportar los datos solicitados imposibilita cumplir con la finalidad o finalidades del tratamiento.

* Decisiones automatizadas, perfiles y lógica aplicada: Los datos no se utilizarán para decisiones automatizadas ni para la elaboración de perfiles. .

* Destinatarios: Sí, con el coordinador del proyecto: Universidad de Navarra

* Transferencia internacional de datos fuera de la UE: No existe

* Conservación de los datos: Se conservarán entre más de 25 años para cumplir con la finalidad para la que se recabaron y para determinar las posibles responsabilidades que

se pudieran derivar de dicha finalidad y del tratamiento de los datos. Una vez transcurrido el tiempo necesario se procederá a la eliminación de todos los datos.

* Derechos: El interesado podrá ejercitar sus derechos de acceso, rectificación, oposición, supresión, portabilidad y limitación del tratamiento, así como, a no ser objeto de decisiones basadas únicamente en el tratamiento automatizado de sus datos, para ello se deberá dirigir mediante solicitud dirigida a la atención de Secretaría General de la UMH, Edificio Rectorado y Consejo Social, Avda. de la Universidad S/N, 03202, Elche-Alicante, o bien a través de sede electrónica <https://sede.umh.es/>. Para cualquier consideración adicional se puede poner en contacto con la delegada de protección de datos: dpd@umh.es. Asimismo, el interesado tiene derecho a presentar una reclamación ante la Autoridad de control (www.aepd.es) si considera que el tratamiento no se ajusta a la normativa vigente.

* Observaciones: Para garantizar la confidencialidad, se procederá a la seudonimización de sus datos. Esto normalmente implica la asignación de un seudónimo (código) a sus datos, de modo que se puedan tratar sin identificarle directamente.

¿CON QUIÉN PUEDO CONTACTAR EN CASO DE DUDA?

Si usted precisa mayor información sobre el estudio puede contactar con ALICIA DE LARA. Teléfono: 965222419; Correo electrónico: a.lara@umh.es

Con el envío de este formulario el estudiantado se da por informado y se entiende su conformidad.

Muchas gracias.

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IBERIFIER – Iberian Digital Media Observatory

IBERIFIER is a digital media observatory in Spain and Portugal funded by the European Commission, linked to the European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO). It is made up of thirteen universities, five fact-checking organizations and news agencies, and five multidisciplinary research centers.

Its main mission is to analyze the Iberian digital media ecosystem and tackle the problem of misinformation. To do this, it focuses its research on five lines of work:

1. Research on the characteristics and trends of the Iberian digital media ecosystem.
2. Development of computational technologies for the early detection of misinformation.
3. Fact-checking of misinformation in the Iberian territory.
4. Strategic reports on threats of disinformation, both for public knowledge and for the authorities of Spain and Portugal.
5. Promotion of media literacy initiatives, aimed at journalists and informants, young people and society as a whole.

For more information, please visit the project website at iberifier.eu

Website: iberifier.eu

X: [@iberifier](https://twitter.com/iberifier)

Instagram: [@iberifier](https://www.instagram.com/iberifier)

LinkedIn: [IBERIFIER](https://www.linkedin.com/company/iberifier)

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Partners

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Co-funded by the European Union

Iberifier – Iberian Digital Media Observatory has received funding from the European Commission under the Call DIGITAL-2023-DEPLOY-04, European Digital Media observatory (EDMO) – National and multinational hubs, with the reference IBERIFIER Plus - 101158511